

REINCARNATE

D3.4 – Advanced valuation models for recycled materials

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Abstract

This report details the advancements in assessing recycled materials for high-performance construction, focusing on the integration of such materials into sustainable building practices and promoting circular economy principles. It outlines the creation of an extensive, open science dataset that merges diverse data from decades of laboratory tests with innovative carbon estimation methodologies. This dataset represents broad data streams provided by the Circular Potential Information Management System (CP-IM), to prioritize materials for recycling while significantly reducing the carbon footprint, especially in concrete applications.

The core of the task involves experimental and computational validations of newly developed, AI-driven design methods—namely, adaptive, and zero-shot designs. These methods drastically cut down the need for extensive lab testing by leveraging artificial intelligence to streamline the exploration and development of complex, sustainable material formulations, aligning with both market needs and environmental goals.

The project's key achievement is the development and real-world validation of the SLAMD software, reaching Technology Readiness Level (TRL)-6. SLAMD operates as a digital twin in the lab, optimizing material properties to meet predefined ecological and economic targets. Its effectiveness has been demonstrated under practical conditions.

Additionally, the report emphasizes the project's dedication to applying these innovations across Europe, with a section devoted to six case studies. These include applications in secondary cementitious materials from waste, designing with recycled aggregates, sustainable asphalt formulations, and data-driven approaches for mid-sized construction sites. Each case study illustrates the real-world benefits and applicability of these methodologies, showcasing their potential to transform sustainable construction practices. The report also highlights the seamless integration of these methods into the CP-IM, enhancing their utility and impact.

Keywords

Recycled High-Performance Materials, Data-Driven Materials Design, Digital Lab Twin, AI-Optimization

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Acronyms and Definitions

Acronym	Meaning
AAC	Alkali-Activated Concrete
AAM	Alkali-Activated Material
AI	Artificial Intelligence
CDW	Construction and Demolition Waste
CP-IM	Circular Potential Information Management System
DDD	Data-Driven Design
DOE	Design of Experiments
FA	Fly Ash
GGBFS	Ground Granulated Blast Furnace Slag
LLM	Large Language Model
RD	Random Draw
RF	Random Forest
SLAMD	Sequential Learning App for Materials Discovery
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
TVD	Test Time Verification Design
W/C	Water-to-Cement Ratio
ZSD	Zero-Shot Design

Reincarnate Project

The average lifespan of a building is 39 years, and factors such as obsolescence and technical limitations often lead to demolition. Consequently, a significant amount of construction and demolition waste (CDW) is generated. Effectively reducing construction waste requires addressing two key aspects: 1) preventing existing buildings from becoming functionally or financially obsolete, and 2) upgrading buildings and their components to extend their lifetime. Despite good intentions, studies have shown that upgradability as a product lifetime extension strategy is limited and reusing entire buildings, building products, or materials in different settings is challenging. These challenges have resulted in a limited use of secondary materials in the building sector. Despite high recycling rates, CDW recycling often leads to downcycling.

Reincarnate aims to advance circular economy practices in the European construction industry by extending the life cycle of buildings, products, and materials, aiming to reduce CDW by 80%, increase reusability by promoting circular economy principles, and lower sector emissions by 70%.

Through the Circular Potential Information Management (CP-IM) platform and associated innovations, Reincarnate will leverage digital technologies like digital twin representation, artificial intelligence, and robotic automation. Building upon three empirically proven social science insights, the project aims to foster the widespread adoption of reused high-quality construction products and materials. Additionally, it will develop business eco-system frameworks to connect actors within sustainable value chains.

Reincarnate's impact will be demonstrated through eleven real-world projects and value chains. Business process guidelines and an e-learning platform will be developed to facilitate the dissemination and exploitation of Reincarnate's results, ultimately contributing to the advancement of circular economy practices in the European construction industry.

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1. Executive Summary

1.1. Goals

This report summarizes the work conducted in the context of Task 3.3 within the Reincarnate project. It targets a transformative approach in the valuation and utilization of recycled materials and materials derived from secondary waste streams, specifically within the building sector. **The primary goal is to facilitate the use of such materials in creating high-performance construction materials, overcoming the current technological barriers to achieving higher circularity, resource efficiency, and reduced carbon footprint in material production.**

The rationale behind this goal is twofold: Firstly, the inherent variability in the composition of secondary raw materials necessitates a departure from traditional, rule-based materials design, which is ill-equipped to handle such variability and complexity. Secondly, the move towards increasing circularity introduces additional formulation challenges due to the blending of various primary and secondary resources, making the development of high-performance materials through traditional trial and error methods inefficient and often ineffective. The complexity of developing sustainable building materials, especially concrete, cannot be overstated.

To address these challenges, the WP proposes a research approach centered on identifying and overcoming the technological constraints that limit material circularity and efficiency. This involves accelerating the materials development process significantly to accommodate the complex and variable nature of secondary raw materials. Furthermore, the WP aims to bridge the gap between theoretical considerations and practical applications by systematically developing use cases that adhere to ecological and economic boundaries, thereby ensuring relevance and impact in real-market scenarios.

By leveraging advanced methodologies, including digital twins and AI-based optimization, the WP seeks to innovate in the development of sustainable building materials, with a particular focus on concrete. This approach aims not only to enhance the technical standards but also to ensure that the solutions developed are viable and impactful within the context of a rapidly evolving building sector. The presented work aspires to set a new benchmark for sustainability in the building sector, aligning with the EU's objectives of promoting a circular economy and reducing environmental footprints.

1.2. Methodology

The methodology of our work package delineates a systematic approach comprising four interconnected stages: **1)** the collection of a comprehensive database of resource streams, **2)** the development of materials design methods, **3)** the transfer of these methodologies to stakeholders through software, and **4)** the

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validation of the software within a real laboratory environment. This structured methodology is designed to ensure a coherent and practical progression from data collection to application.

1) Collecting a database of a resource stream

The foundational step in our methodology involves the creation of a detailed and representative database focused on alternative sustainable building materials, with a particular emphasis on concrete formulations utilizing waste and industrial by-product-based binders. This database was constructed to model the complexity and variability inherent in sustainable building materials, offering a significant advancement in the field by providing a robust data basis for material design and innovation.

In selecting alternative concrete as the focus, our work directly addresses Reincarnates mission to reduce both the reliance on primary resources and the carbon footprint associated with conventional construction materials. Ordinary Portland cement, the most common binder used in concrete, is responsible for approximately 8% of human-made CO₂ emissions. The alternative binders featured in our database present a potential CO₂ footprint reduction of up to 80%.

The data set builds a solid foundation for the subsequent stages of the methodology, ensuring that the development of new materials design methods, the transfer of knowledge through software, and the validation processes are grounded in comprehensive and representative data.

2) Developing materials design methods

In the subsequent phase of our methodology within the EU Horizon project, we concentrate on advancing the development of materials design methods. This stage is critical for reducing the necessity for extensive experimental validation in the development of new materials, thus facilitating the exploration of more complex, yet sustainable, material formulations. Our approach is bifurcated into two innovative design methodologies: adaptive design and zero-shot design.

Adaptive design is aimed at swiftly fine-tuning complex material compositions to meet specific requirements and desired properties. The essence of this approach lies in its capacity to mitigate the challenges posed by the high design complexity and the unpredictable nature of secondary raw materials' compositions. By adopting an adaptive framework, the method utilizes real-world experimental outcomes as direct feedback for the artificial intelligence (AI) model, thereby refining and enhancing material designs iteratively with minimal initial data. This adaptive loop ensures the development of safe, high-quality materials by continuously improving design accuracy and efficacy with each iteration.

Contrastingly, **zero-shot design** represents a paradigm shift in materials development, enabling the generation of material designs without the prerequisite of training data. This approach leverages pre-trained

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large language models (LLMs) to conceptualize designs based on a set of requirements and iteratively optimize them by drawing on the LLMs' vast repository of engineering knowledge and practices. Zero-shot design is particularly adept at handling the variability and complexity inherent in sustainable material formulations, optimizing resource flow and material composition in alignment with best engineering practices.

The **Data-driven Design Development** process has been carried out following these key steps:

- The simulation of high-performance material development under real-world laboratory conditions using our comprehensive dataset.
- A rigorous statistical analysis of the performance of AI designs, with a focus on evaluating the lower confidence interval to ensure high confidence in the results.
- A comparative analysis with traditional statistical baseline methods to benchmark the effectiveness and efficiency of the AI-driven approaches.

This methodological development stage is instrumental in transcending traditional barriers in sustainable materials development, enabling a significant reduction in experimental validation needs. By harnessing the power of AI, specifically through adaptive and zero-shot design, we can unlock the potential for more complex and environmentally friendly material solutions.

3) Transfer to practice through SLAMD software

Transitioning from the development of innovative materials design methods to practical application, the third phase of our methodology involves the creation and dissemination of a specialized software tool, SLAMD (Sequential Learning App for Materials Discovery). This phase is pivotal in operationalizing the data-driven design approach, ensuring that the theoretical and methodological advancements made in the project are accessible and utilizable by a broader audience, particularly stakeholders in the construction materials sector. Currently, due to the lack of data sets from other materials such as glass, steel, ceramic and etc., we use concrete data sets to optimize the process of finding materials with desired features.

SLAMD functions as a digital laboratory twin, offering users the ability to input detailed information about available resources, including ecological and economic footprint data derived from the CP-IM. The second core functionality of SLAMD revolves around its AI-Optimization feature, which empowers users to define complex composite design targets. This AI-driven engine is designed to navigate the intricacies of materials design, allowing for the optimization of formulations based on the specified targets and available data. Moreover, SLAMD is equipped with various data dashboards that enhance the user experience by providing insightful analytics and support throughout the design process.

A critical aspect of SLAMD is its accessibility and ease of use. To achieve widespread adoption and facilitate user engagement, the software has been developed as open-source Python software. This choice not only

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promotes transparency and collaboration within the scientific community but also ensures that SLAMD can be continuously improved and adapted to meet evolving needs. Additionally, by web-hosting the tool, we have significantly lowered the barriers to entry, allowing easy access for interested users worldwide.

The development and deployment of SLAMD embody the project's commitment to bridging the gap between theoretical research and practical application. By providing a robust, user-friendly platform for materials discovery, SLAMD plays a crucial role in advancing the goals of the Reincarnate project, facilitating the development of sustainable building materials, and contributing to the broader objectives of resource efficiency and carbon footprint reduction in the construction sector.

4) Validation of SLAMD in a real-world laboratory environment

The final phase of our methodology involves the practical validation of the SLAMD software, pivotal for achieving Technology Readiness Level (TRL)-6 status. This validation was carried out through a comparative laboratory study, benchmarking SLAMD against traditional materials design methods, specifically the Design of Experiments (DOE). The objective of this experimental study was to develop a high-performance, waste-based binder. The study utilized slag derived from the glass production process, amalgamating various residual and correction materials. This waste slag, initially inert, was rendered reactive through the introduction of a complex-compound activator liquid, incorporating by-products.

This scenario typifies the challenges inherent in developing sustainable alternative cements, where the goal is not merely to react a consistent powder with tap water. Instead, it involves the intricate adjustment of multiple activator components to ensure a robust reaction with slag, which itself exhibits significant compositional variability. Such complexity in material systems is beyond the scope of conventional design methods.

The software's AI-Optimization enabled the efficient tuning of material formulations to meet the ambitious design target safely. This validation exercise was not merely a test of SLAMD's technical capabilities but also a demonstration of its practical applicability and effectiveness in a real-world lab situation.

1.3. Key Findings

The comprehensive efforts of our work have culminated in several key findings that underscore the innovative potential and practical applicability of our methodologies and tools in the sustainable construction materials sector. These findings highlight the unique aspects of our database, the effectiveness of adaptive and zero-shot material design methodologies, and the groundbreaking role of AI in accelerating sustainable material development.

The creation of a detailed and high-quality database represents a significant achievement of this project. The dataset encompasses up to 80 composition features across more than 1600 concrete formulations. It

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includes critical properties such as compressive strength and workability, essential for assessing the practical viability of the materials. Furthermore, the dataset incorporates a simplified Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) approach, adding a layer of ecological resource information by estimating the CO₂ footprint associated with each formulation.

A comprehensive computational study was undertaken to evaluate the adaptive material design methodologies developed in this project. Contrary to common expectations that high-accuracy predictive models are essential for rapid material development, our research suggests that a practical framework for material design suffices. This framework significantly reduces development time and costs while allowing for the simultaneous optimization of material costs and environmental impacts. This finding not only accelerates the development of sustainable materials but also ensures their alignment with market needs and sustainability objectives.

LLMs have been identified as a novel approach that can even outperform traditional methods in the design of sustainable concrete. LLMs leverage (fuzzy) design knowledge in natural language, a largely untapped data modality in AI-driven materials design, making the process more intuitive and accessible. By applying techniques from mathematical problem-solving, LLMs refine their outputs based on real-world laboratory feedback, demonstrating the potential of AI systems to address complex challenges with limited initial data.

The project's experimental study aimed to validate our software tool SLAMD under real-world conditions. A design campaign has been conducted using our tool to develop high-performance, alkali-activated materials using secondary precursors, with a target compressive strength exceeding 100 MPa after 7 days. The results reveal that AI-driven design methodologies significantly outperform classic design methods in both development speed and material quality.

The successful development of a waste-based binder is a testament to the software's advanced design and optimization capabilities. This achievement not only validates the software under real-world conditions rendering it TRL-6, but also highlights the potential for a new market segment focused on high-performance, sustainable construction materials. A noteworthy aspect of our findings is the accessibility and usability of the developed AI design methods. The experimental campaign was executed by a civil engineering bachelor student, without extensive expertise in materials design or AI. Following a brief initial training, the student successfully conducted the study, highlighting the software's potential to lower the access threshold to advanced AI design methodologies significantly. This underscores the user-friendly nature of our software.

1.4. Conclusions

Within Reincarnates Task 3.3 significant strides have been made towards advancing the field of sustainable construction materials through the integration of innovative data sets, machine learning methodologies, and software tools. This work has not only demonstrated significant advancements in the design and

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development of circular materials but has also provided a roadmap for integrating environmental considerations, specifically CO₂ data, into material design processes. The final software developed achieves Technology Readiness Level (TRL)-6, validating its efficacy and applicability in real-world settings. Furthermore, the methodologies and approaches developed offer promising possibilities for generalization to other material types, extending the impact of this work beyond its initial scope.

The creation of a unique, detailed, and high-quality data set stands as a cornerstone achievement of this project. This data set, enriched with LCA data, offers an unprecedented resource for the development of DDD methods focused on sustainable concrete. It has enabled a more nuanced understanding of material properties and environmental impacts, laying a solid foundation for further innovation in material design.

The development and application of adaptive and zero-shot design methodologies, powered by machine learning and LLMs, represent a leap forward in materials science. These methodologies have drastically reduced the need for extensive experimental validation, enabling the exploration of more complex and sustainable material formulations. By harnessing the power of AI, these methods have demonstrated the potential to significantly accelerate the development process while simultaneously optimizing for cost, performance, and environmental impact.

The inclusion of CO₂ data from the Circular Potential Information Model (CP-IM) into the material design process is a testament to the project's commitment to sustainability. This integration allows for a holistic view of material impacts, ensuring that the development of new materials not only focuses on technical performance but also on reducing environmental footprints. This approach signifies a paradigm shift in how materials are designed, emphasizing the importance of sustainability in the construction industry.

The development of SLAMD and its validation at a TRL-6 level under real-world conditions underscore the practical applicability and effectiveness of the software. This validation confirms SLAMD's role as a pivotal tool in the sustainable materials design process, offering an intuitive, accessible, and powerful platform for both experts and novices in the field. The open-source nature and web-hosting of SLAMD further enhance its accessibility, promoting widespread adoption and collaborative improvement.

The methodologies and tools developed in this project hold significant potential for generalization to other materials, suggesting a broad applicability of the approaches beyond sustainable concrete. This potential for generalization opens new avenues for research and development across various materials and sectors, offering the promise of a more sustainable and efficient approach to materials science.

Partner input: What cases come to mind?

The achievements of this project not only address the immediate goals set forth but also lay the groundwork for future advancements in the broader quest for sustainability and efficiency in construction and beyond.

2. Introduction and Background

The construction industry stands as one of the most significant consumers of primary resources globally, contributing substantially to environmental degradation through high levels of carbon dioxide emissions and resource depletion. The urgency to shift towards sustainable practices is underscored by the fact that approximately half of all materials produced by humanity are allocated to construction activities, with concrete being the most prevalent. Despite its ubiquity, the production of concrete, particularly Portland cement, is responsible for approximately eight percent of anthropogenic CO₂ emissions [1], driven primarily by the energy-intensive processes of burning and the decarbonization of limestone. These emissions not only exacerbate climate change but also spotlight the unsustainable reliance on primary resources within the industry.

Against the backdrop of escalating environmental challenges, the European Green Deal and international targets for carbon neutrality by 2050 [2] necessitate a profound transformation within the construction sector. This transformation is envisioned through the increased circularity in construction practices, aiming to reduce dependency on primary resources and significantly curtail CO₂ emissions. However, the realization of this vision is impeded by several critical factors related to the use of secondary resources and the design of construction materials.

Figure 1 : Oxide composition of Ordinary Portland Cement made from primary resources vs. composition of environmentally friendly alternatives from waste slags, fly ashes and natural Pozzolans. Combinatorial designs spanned by alternative resources with high performance materials marked in pink and low performance materials marked in turquoise.

Historically, secondary resources have been relegated to low-value applications, such as fillers beneath streets, representing a significant underutilization of their potential. To transition towards a more circular construction industry, there is a pressing need to elevate these materials into high-performance applications, thereby achieving up-cycling rather than down-cycling. This approach not only conserves primary resources but also harnesses the inherent value in secondary materials. Nevertheless, the adoption of secondary

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resources is fraught with challenges, primarily due to their inconsistent composition (cf oxide distribution of OPC and alternative resources in Figure 1), and the complex nature of waste-based materials, which contain a more diverse array of constituents and supplements (compare compositions in Figure 2) compared to primary resources [3].

The variability and complexity of secondary materials render traditional material design approaches, which rely on the predictability and uniformity of primary resources, largely ineffective. This is exemplified in cases of more sustainable cementitious materials, where the empirical and prescriptive nature of conventional development methodologies struggles to address the extensive range of compositional variations and the nuanced chemical reactions involved [4].

Figure 2: Trade-off between Performance in terms of ecological impact and formulation complexity at the example of concrete with increased formulation complexity with lower ecological impact.

Concrete production has witnessed initial successes in embracing circularity through the innovative use of byproducts, such as fly ash and granulated blast furnace slag, as secondary supplements for traditional cement. These successes have not only demonstrated the feasibility of reducing dependencies on primary resources but have also contributed to the reduction of the environmental footprint associated with traditional cementitious materials. The utilization of such byproducts exemplifies the potential for increased circularity within the industry, showcasing tangible benefits in terms of both environmental impact and resource efficiency.

However, the future availability of these established secondary materials is becoming increasingly uncertain, primarily due to global shifts towards sustainable energy sources and the consequent decline in coal-fired power generation [5, 6]. Additionally, the transformation of industrial processes, such as the conversion of blast furnaces to cleaner alternatives, further complicates the reliable sourcing of materials like granulated blast furnace slag [7]. This emerging scarcity not only underscores the fragility of current successes but also highlights the inherent risks associated with relying on a limited pool of secondary resources.

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Moreover, while the initial applications of byproducts as secondary materials have marked a step in the right direction, they also illuminate a critical issue: the pace at which the construction industry integrates more diverse secondary resources is considerably slow. The current approach, though effective in isolated instances, lacks the scalability and agility needed to fully embrace the breadth of materials available for circular construction practices. The dual challenges of resource scarcity and slow adoption rates starkly illustrate that achieving circularity in construction requires not only the identification of new secondary materials but also a paradigm shift in materials design and application methodologies. This shift must be capable of rapidly adapting to the changing availability of resources and the complex compositions of waste-based materials, ensuring that the industry can sustain its progress towards circularity without interruption.

2.1. Literature Review Data-Driven Materials Design

The application of machine learning (ML) techniques in the realm of building materials design has seen significant growth, propelled by the complex nature of these materials and their varying properties. Early attempts to utilize computer-aided approaches for material design encountered limitations due to the lack of advanced computing power and sophisticated ML methods [8]. However, recent developments have greatly expanded the potential for innovative material design. Studies such as those by Naderpour et al. [9], Chaabene et al. [10], and Li et al. [11] have demonstrated the application of artificial neural networks (ANNs), support vector machines, and other ML techniques to predict and optimize the properties of environmentally friendly concrete mixtures, highlighting the critical importance of data preparation, model validation, and interpretation.

Particularly in concrete science, the integration of ML with evolutionary algorithms and generative design has enabled the discovery of novel concrete mixtures that balance compressive strength with environmental considerations such as CO₂ emission reduction and cost efficiency [12, 13, 14, 15]. A detailed review on combining ML algorithms with evolutionary approaches is summarized by Song et al. [16]. Despite these advancements, the reliance on large datasets for training ML algorithms presents a significant challenge due to the expensive and time-consuming nature of data collection in this field.

However, the advent of Adaptive Design strategies has marked a departure from traditional data-intensive ML approaches, offering a pathway to accelerate materials design with considerably less data [17, 18]. Rather than relying either on time-consuming laboratory validation or large scale data sets, optimization frameworks such as Sequential Learning (SL) and the closely related Bayesian Experimental Design (BED) [17] create a data-driven feedback loop: From a variety of possible formulations, SL predicts the most promising candidate materials, which are then empirically validated in the laboratory. Instead of calculating the parameters for an ideal formulation directly, ML models optimize formulations in an iterative cycle of predictions and validations. Studies by Ling et al. [19], Rohr et al. [20], and Völker et al. [21] have showcased the efficacy of SL in materials discovery and design, including its superior performance in detecting alkali-

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activated binders with fewer data points and processing a larger number of features than conventional ML methods.

Additionally, the emergence of LLMs has introduced a novel paradigm to materials design. LLMs leverage their vast knowledge base for adaptive prediction [22]. Foundational models like GPT-3.5 and GPT-4 have demonstrated remarkable capabilities in zero-shot learning, allowing for the generation of material designs without the prerequisite of extensive training data [22].

A key novelty of LLMs is their use of fuzzy domain knowledge as context in natural language, a largely untapped data modality in AI-driven material design. This utilisation of natural language simplifies complex AI processes, making the design process more accessible to a diverse range of researchers and practitioners. The LLM approach is characterised by its virtual independence from traditional training data, which may represent a breakthrough in material development with variable and volatile starting materials. This breakthrough has significant implications for materials science, enabling the exploration of new material formulations with unprecedented speed and flexibility.

Jablonka et al. [23] demonstrates that LLMs can outperform traditional machine learning models predicting molecular material properties, and chemical reactions, especially in scenarios with limited data in chemistry. Another study by Ramos et al. [24] shows the success of LLMs in predicting the solubility of drug-like molecules and reaction yields, including uncertainty estimates, using context in natural language, which performed on par with conventional models.

While Sequential Learning and LLMs present promising new directions for materials design, their application to sustainable concrete raises several research questions. The potential of these methods to handle the variable composition of sustainable materials, incorporate critical factors such as resource availability, CO₂ footprint, and cost, and maintain the required standards of safety and reliability in engineering applications remains an crucial area of interest. Furthermore, the capacity of LLMs to utilize fuzzy design context and perform effectively in zero-shot scenarios highlights an exciting avenue for research, suggesting a paradigm shift in how materials are designed and optimized.

As the construction industry advances towards more sustainable practices, the exploration of adaptive and zero-shot design strategies for concrete represents a critical and underexplored frontier. Our project situates itself within this evolving landscape, aiming to address the gaps in current research by evaluating the efficacy of Sequential Learning and Large Language Models in the development of sustainable concrete formulations. By focusing on concrete as an ideal candidate for sustainable material design, our study seeks to contribute to the broader effort of reducing the environmental impact of construction materials, paving the way for a more sustainable and resource-efficient future.

3. Methodology

This chapter outlines the methodologies that are fundamental to our research, beginning with an exploration of the distinctions between traditional prescriptive design approaches and contemporary ML-based strategies. We also discuss how LLMs can be effectively applied to design tasks, providing a fresh perspective on their potential within our field. Additionally, we present a framework for the rigorous statistical assessment of ML-based design methods, ensuring that our approaches are both scientifically valid and practically applicable. The chapter concludes with a detailed explanation of our data collection and curation processes, which are essential for building a robust and reliable foundation for our work program. All the development was completed during the Reincarnate project. Through these sections, we aim to elucidate the innovative techniques that drive our project and underscore their importance in advancing sustainable material development.

3.1. ML driven Inverse Materials Design

In the world of construction material development, the traditional path has always been straightforward yet rigid: start with a specific formula to guarantee certain material properties, such as strength or durability, and then validate these properties through extensive laboratory testing. This approach, heavily reliant on empirical data and predefined formulations, has served the industry well, especially in environments where the composition of materials and their resulting properties are well-understood and relatively stable.

However, as the construction industry increasingly turns towards recycling materials to meet sustainability goals, a new challenge emerges. Recycled materials, by their very nature, introduce variability and complexity into the design process (cf. **Error! Reference source not found.** and Figure 2) that traditional methods are ill-equipped to handle. The empirical relationships and "forward rules" that once guided material formulation no longer apply uniformly, leaving a gap in our ability to predict material performance. This is exemplified in Figure 3 where the mix designs in the (center) derived from regulations and standards (left) assure a high applicable quality for common concretes (grey curve right) but fail to deliver the same applicable lower-bound performance for more sustainable yet inconsistent resources (yellow curve).

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Figure 3: Traditional, linear prescriptive design approach. Formulations (center) are derived from regulations and standards (left), which provide high quality for peristant resources (right: gray curve) but fail to assure high quality for recycling materials (right: yellow curve).

This is where the concept of inverse design offers a solution. Instead of starting with a prescribed formula, the inverse design (ID) method flips the script. It begins with the end in mind—the desired material properties—and uses ML algorithms to explore a vast set of potential formulations to find those that are most likely to deliver on those properties [25]. Effectively, this means turning a (forward) design process into a (backwards or inverse) search problem in which the most promising materials composition is identified by matching predicted properties with the set of requirements specified by the engineer.

Figure 4: Inverse design accelerating materials development. Left: Iterative Inverse Design Workflow with 1) data collection, 2) model training, 3) predicting properties of materials candidates in design space and 4) selecting best candidate for validation. Right: Inverse design outpacing classic design approaches through quick feedback loops.

The inverse design workflow, which is shown in Figure 4, (left), begins by 1) testing a preliminary set of material formulations in the laboratory to evaluate their real-world performance. This initial data is then used to 2) train a machine learning model, which serves as the foundation for the next step: 3) predicting the properties of a vast number of material formulations in what is known as the design space (DS). The DS

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contains all feasible variations of mix designs, including those that with non-obvious outcomes which previously have been considered only incidentally.

From this extensive pool of candidates, the model identifies and selects the formulations that best meet the specified design requirements. These selected materials are 4) subsequently validated in the laboratory to confirm their performance. The results from these validations are integrated back into the dataset, enriching the initial data.

This cyclical process—test, predict, select, and validate—forms a feedback loop that efficiently narrows down the most promising materials, accelerating the path to identifying the optimal design. Through this iterative cycle, the ID approach dynamically refines the search and enhances the precision of material selection, ensuring continual improvement in the development of construction materials (see Figure 4, right).

Importantly, identifying successful materials in the design space is not constrained by simple rules but is instead defined by the potential of every conceivable material combination, i.e. we're not just tweaking a few parameters within a narrow range of known materials. We're embarking on a comprehensive search that considers all possible materials, including those that might have been overlooked or deemed non-obvious by traditional standards. **This is not merely thinking outside the box; it's acknowledging that the box is much larger and more diverse than previously imagined.**

What sets the inverse design approach apart is not just its expansive search capability but also its ability to incorporate a multi-faceted set of objectives into the search process. This is where traditional methods, with their focus on single or limited parameters falls short. Inverse design, however, considers a wide array of information, from predicted material properties to critical factors like environmental impact, cost, and availability, all sourced from innovative tools like the **CP-IM**.

This holistic view allows for a nuanced material selection process that goes beyond mere technical suitability. It aims to identify formulations that not only meet the desired performance criteria but do so in a way that aligns with broader sustainability and cost-efficiency goals. It's a method that not only asks, "Will this work?" but also, "Will this work best for our needs, now and in the future?"

3.2. LLM based Materials Design

In this section of our report, we introduce a novel ID methodology: the use of LLMs. This approach not only complements the machine learning strategies outlined previously but also introduces a novel dimension to handling the complexities of sustainable material development.

Traditional data-driven approaches, while effective, can struggle with the dynamic and complex nature of sustainable materials. They exhibit high variability batch-to-batch, making it impractical to rely solely on pre-

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existing data. Typically, this necessitates a preliminary phase of data collection to establish fundamental relationships, which can delay the development of new formulations.

To address these challenges, we have integrated Foundational LLMs into our ID process. LLMs, known for their extensive world knowledge and adaptability, offer a promising solution by enabling In-Context Learning (ICL). This capability allows LLMs to interpret fuzzy rules and instructions and apply them to generate tangible material designs within an evolving context. Such adaptability is particularly valuable in navigating the ambiguous terrains of material design, where little data might exist, but fuzzy design rules can be expressed in natural language. LLMs leverage this context allowing for a more flexible adaptation to new and diverse material design scenarios.

The simplest implementation of this technology in our project is the Zero-Shot Design (ZSD) workflow (see Figure 5). In ZSD, a Design Assistant (DA) powered by an LLM engages in a feedback loop with the user, generating material design suggestions that meet specified requirements through an inverse design approach. These suggestions are then validated through laboratory experiments, with findings fed back into the model to refine future proposals. This loop embodies a direct, chat-based interaction where the user effectively communicates with the model to refine material properties and design objectives.

Figure 5: Zero-Shot Design (ZSD) workflow: Feedback loop between the user's lab validation data and the Design Assistant's suggested design.

Building on the foundation of ZSD, we propose an enhanced chat-based design strategy named Test Time Verification Design (TVD). This strategy, which has previously been suggested for solving math problems [26, 27], involves not only generating multiple design suggestions but also evaluating these proposals through a second LLM, the so-called Verifier Model (VM) (see Figure 6). The VM analyzes the DA's designs, predicts their expected properties (e.g. compressive strength), and ranks them according to their potential effectiveness. This dual-layered approach allows for a more rigorous assessment of each design proposal, ensuring that only the most promising formulations are selected for laboratory validation.

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Figure 6: Testing and Verification Design (TVD): Inverse design loop and forward prediction loop. Implementation with test time equal to three. Task instructions and design knowledge are provided to the DA and the VM respectively via the system message.

Both ZSD and TVD illustrate the power of LLMs in simplifying the complex processes involved in material design. The key difference between this approach and the traditional ID methods described in the previous chapter (such as SL and BED) is that the explicit creation of the DS is not required. Instead, the formulations can be generated directly from the LLMs, which significantly simplifies the ID approach.

Furthermore, by employing these models and their zero-shot designs, we can bypass some of the more labor-intensive steps traditionally associated with material development, such as extensive preliminary data collection and experimentation. Instead, we leverage the model's ability to generate informed predictions and recommendations based on a comprehensive understanding of the material's properties and the desired outcomes.

The integration of LLMs into our material design process represents a significant methodological innovation, providing a flexible and powerful tool for developing sustainable materials.

3.3. Benchmarking Materials Design

The promise of both the traditional inverse design approach and the novel LLM based method is clear, offering a path to discovering innovative materials that could significantly reduce the environmental footprint of the construction industry. However, at its core they are powered by imperfect predictive models. Consequently, the looming question remains:

Are AI-powered design approaches effective enough to stand up to the complexities and demands of the real market?

This is the central question that our work sought out to address. By moving beyond the theoretical and into the practical application of design methods in construction materials, we aim to benchmark their

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effectiveness, scalability, and adaptability to real-world conditions. As we transition into discussing our benchmarking approach, the focus will shift to validating the design method against the rigorous standards and unpredictable variables. It is here that we will explore not just the potential of this approach but its practicality, aiming to demonstrate that the future of sustainable construction material design is not only imaginable but achievable.

Traditionally, the performance of ML models is assessed by metrics such as accuracy or success rate. However, when it comes to concrete design, these conventional metrics like root-mean-square error (RMSE) may not adequately reflect the approaches effectiveness in practical applications.

In the unique context of materials design, the crucial measure of success is not just the accuracy of the predictions but how efficiently the model can guide the design process to discover materials that meet desired properties within constrained timelines and lab budgets. Surprisingly, we found that lower RMSE does not necessarily correlate with a model's ability to successfully identify target materials in a real lab setting. This revelation shifts the focus towards evaluating the practical application of these models in a laboratory environment.

To address this, we conduct simulated experiments that mimic real-world conditions to measure the ID process's performance. The effectiveness of ID is best demonstrated through simulations using large sets of published data, where the outcomes of all potential formulations are known a-priori, allowing for automated exploration of the design space under varied initial conditions. This method provides a robust statistical measure of performance based on the duration and number of development cycles required to identify materials with the desired properties. Since LLMs can output any design, even those not included in our data, their output was constrained by clear instructions to the available datasets.

The benchmarking workflow for these simulations is as follows: Initially, the ID algorithm is provided with a subset of available data for initial training of the prediction model, represented in Figure 7 in green (ZSD does not require initial training data and simply skips this part). As the development cycle progress, the algorithm selects the data point predicted to be the most promising, indicated by red arrows until a material is found that meets the specific requirements, marked in blue in Figure 7. The key metric of success for these simulations is the number of development cycles necessary to achieve materials that match the target properties, highlighted in blue in Figure 7.

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Figure 7: Workflow of ID-benchmarking experiments; Top: ID iteratively samples a given DS starting with n randomized initial samples (marked in yellow) to find target materials (marked in green); Bottom: Histogram of required samples with 50% and 90% success probability.

The outcomes of numerous benchmarking experiments can be presented as a distribution of the number of cycles required to meet the target properties. A particular focus lies on the lower-bound performance (90% prob. of success in Figure 7, bottom) mirroring the lower bound rule used in approving civil engineering materials in Europe, which ensures that materials adhere to essential safety and reliability standards. This benchmark, emphasizing the worst-case performance rather than average results, providing a realistic assessment of each method's practical applicability, especially in safety-critical applications.

To establish a baseline for comparison, ID is often juxtaposed against a random draw (RD) approach, where experiments are conducted haphazardly without any strategic guidance or predictive modeling. The success probability in RD is statistically estimated using the hypergeometric distribution, serving as a stark contrast to the more directed and potentially more efficient ID approach.

Crucially, the materials selected for validation in each development cycle of ID are not merely theoretical but are drawn from actual laboratory results documented extensively in prior studies. This practical foundation enhances the relevance of our findings to real-world applications. Each formulation is backed by laboratory-determined compressive strengths, a vital property for concrete performance. These datasets are meticulously curated (as described in chapter XX) to ensure uniformity in specimen shape, dimensions, and testing age to maintain consistency across tests. Additionally, each data point includes CO₂ footprint assessments derived from established literature, integrating an environmental benchmark into our evaluations as well.

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This systematic approach not only confirms the feasibility of the ID method under controlled experimental conditions but also underscores its potential applicability and effectiveness in the dynamic and demanding realm of real-market construction materials development.

3.4. Data Collection

A high-quality data set plays a central role in the methodological developments within the Reincarnate project. Thus, a comprehensive set of data describing the properties of recycled materials was created, made publicly available [28] and published in the “Data in Brief” journal [29]. This data set specifically focuses on concrete formulations and their corresponding properties, utilizing binders based on secondary resources known as alkali-activated concrete (AAC). The binders are crucial for the high performance of the concrete, and due to their complex composition, they are ideal candidates for our design study. The dataset is exemplary in its scope and utility, meaning that although the primary focus is on waste-based concrete, the methodologies developed are transferable to other materials such as glass, steel, ceramics, and aluminium.

Figure 8: Data collection workflow. From left to right: a. represents the set of research papers that study the different features of AAC. [1] selected in b. a subset of these papers that served their research goals. The interest of this compilation in the AAC community made the c. data curation process worth the effort. The format of the data is ready for the d. data-driven applications.

The open science data set comprises a complex material data space sourced from various publications and our internal databases. This data has been meticulously curated and enriched (Figure 8), forming a comprehensive and accessible resource that not only supports our research objectives but also aligns with broader goals of sustainable material development.

Our dataset includes a wide array of AAC formulations, each detailed with compressive strength measurements and CO₂ footprint calculations. These footprints are derived from the CO₂ values of the materials' constituents, which we sourced from existing literature. This dual focus on mechanical strength and environmental impact reflects the critical properties required for selecting concrete for various applications, emphasizing the need for materials that are not only structurally sound but also environmentally responsible.

To enhance the utility of this dataset, we've included additional properties where possible, such as porosity, abrasion, and workability. While the coverage of these additional properties is not as extensive as we might

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wish, they enrich the dataset and provide a fuller picture of each material's characteristics. Acknowledging the importance of these attributes, we anticipate that future research will continue to expand on these areas, contributing to a more comprehensive understanding of AACs.

Structurally, the dataset is organized into a single table that integrates all this information, making it straightforward for researchers to access and analyze. The data is categorized into several key areas:

1. **Identification Features** – Each AAC formulation is given a unique identifier that links back to detailed reference sources, ensuring traceability and ease of reference.
2. **Binder Oxides Composition** – This section details the molecular composition of binder powders in weight percent, providing insights into the chemical reactivity of the constituents. For mixtures utilizing multiple binders, a weighted ratio is calculated, offering a detailed breakdown for each oxide molecule.
3. **Aggregate and Activator Content** – We include specifics on the types and quantities of aggregates used, as well as the chemical composition and concentration of alkali activators, which are crucial for understanding the material's performance.
4. **Curing and Workability Features** – Details such as curing conditions and workability modifiers like water and superplasticizers are documented, which are essential for replicating and understanding the curing process and the mix's behavior during application.
5. **Comprehensive Material Properties** – The dataset extends to properties of both fresh and cured AAC specimens, including mechanical and structural attributes, which are indispensable for assessing the material's suitability for specific applications.

The data validation and curation process were carefully executed to ensure the dataset's reliability and applicability. We began by reviewing and selecting pertinent studies, followed by a rigorous examination to correct any discrepancies and remove redundancies. This process involved not only the standardization of units and measures but also the careful consideration of the dataset's completeness and the relevance of each included feature.

Furthermore, the CO₂ footprints included in our dataset consider both the production and extraction impacts of the constituent materials and, where applicable, the effects of oven curing. This comprehensive approach to calculating environmental impact underlines our commitment to fostering sustainable practices in material development.

In sum, this dataset not only serves as a fundamental benchmark for AAC characterization but also acts as a dynamic tool for the AAC community. It aids in identifying research gaps, provides essential data for predictive modeling, and sets a standard for evaluating AAC concretes in the industry. As this dataset

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continues to evolve with contributions from the global research community, it will undoubtedly enhance its value and utility, driving forward the development of sustainable building materials.

4. Experimental Studies

In this chapter two main experimental studies are described which were conducted to evaluate and refine data-driven methods aimed at enhancing the precise valuation of recycled materials. The first study was a large-scale exploration using ML driven Inverse Materials Design. This approach leveraged the sophisticated modeling capabilities of ML to predict the properties of recycled materials from varied input data, effectively allowing for optimized material formulations based on desired performance characteristics.

The second study explored the application of LLMs for Materials Design. This novel approach utilized the advanced processing power of LLMs to interpret and generate material compositions using natural language inputs, making the technology accessible and intuitive for users without deep technical expertise in data science.

Both studies were pivotal, building upon the foundational methods and datasets discussed in the previous chapters. They were designed to rigorously assess the effectiveness of these innovative approaches under varied, real-world inspired conditions. The outcomes of these studies are crucial, providing a deeper understanding of the capabilities and limitations of these cutting-edge technologies in practical applications. These experiments not only validate the methods developed but also enhance our ability to accurately predict and improve the properties of recycled materials, thus supporting more sustainable practices in material usage and contributing significantly to the field of materials science.

4.1. Large Scale Benchmarking Case study for Data driven design of sustainable concrete.

In this case study, published in the Journal of cleaner Production [30], we scrutinize the practical application and viability of the ID approach using SL in real-world settings, specifically targeting the development of sustainable building materials. Our research delves into an array of configurations and optimization scenarios to discern the most effective strategies for employing SL in material design, especially focusing on AAC.

The foundation of our research is built on data gathered from 49 distinct sources, yielding a total of 1,367 concrete formulations with known compressive strengths and CO₂ footprints (see chapter 3.4 for more details on the data collection). The data has been formatted into nine distinct search spaces to ensure consistency in specimen shape, dimensions, and testing conditions. The design targets were two-fold. First, the formulations above the 95% quantile were sought after, which represent the top 5% high performing materials within each search space. Second the optimal trade-off between high strength and low CO₂ footprint were sought after. The experiments were repeated 25 times and assessed in terms of the required development cycles required by the respective ID approach (cf. experimental program in Figure 9).

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Figure 9: Outlining the experimental program. Left: composition of the search spaces in terms of number of references, number of concrete recipes, and number of descriptive parameters. Center: Targets: maximum compressive strength and minimum CO₂ footprint. Right: Type of Benchmarking.

The underlying hypothesis was that the proper configuration of the design process is key to its success. Our setup allowed us to explore key questions around design configuration that are particularly relevant to practitioners considering ID applications. Answering these questions is an essential step in reducing application boundaries. We investigated the following, among others:

Q1: Which **ML-algorithm** is best suited for ID?

Q2: How much **training data** is required to start ID?

Q3: Does environmentally **informed AI** improve performance?

To answer Q1, our experimental design utilized two widely recognized machine learning models: Gaussian Process Regression (GPR) and Random Forest (RF). Both techniques are considered non-parametric, meaning that they do not make assumptions about the functional form of the data and can flexibly adapt to complex patterns in the data. The effectiveness of various model configurations, including hyperparameter settings and pre-processing techniques, was rigorously tested.

Q2, addressed the initial training set size which has been varied between 4 and 20 samples. While these numbers are arbitrary, they were chosen to represent two distinct scenarios that might occur in practical applications. A smaller set of 4 samples simulates a situation where laboratory capacity or resources are limited, often the case when developing entirely new materials. Conversely, a larger set of 20 samples reflects scenarios where more data is readily available, such as when fine-tuning well-known materials for novel applications like high-performance or ecologically engineered materials.

Q3, compares two different optimization scenarios. Single objective optimization is performed first, in which materials with high compressive strength are sought. This optimization represents a laboratory-driven

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approach, where only predicted material strength is considered for decision-making. It is the most common case in the material optimization literature. For the second optimization target, the best compromise between CO₂ footprint and strength is sought. This optimization scenario represents a more practical-oriented approach, in which the suitability of a material for a particular application may depend on a whole range of properties that do not have to come exclusively from the lab but could also be derived from our CP-IM.

4.1.1. Key Findings and Innovations

The study highlighted several critical insights. The comparative analysis of the models (Q1) is shown in Figure 10 below and compared against RD as the base line. The results show that all models tested outperformed the random draw (RD) baseline, which underscores the efficacy of the SL approach in accelerating the development of new materials. However, in line with the "no-free-lunch" theorem, we found that no single model or pipeline consistently outperformed others across various scenarios. This finding challenges the common focus in scientific discourse on model selection and hyperparameter tuning. Contrary to expectations, these factors did not yield measurable advantages in the tested scenarios. For practitioners, this underscores that the implementation of an SL framework itself is more critical than the choice of specific models within that framework, as the SL approach demonstrated clear effectiveness across the board.

Figure 10: Comparing the performance in terms of required development cycles for different model-pipeline configuration across 900 experiments respectively.

Figure 11 summarizes the results of Q2. The size of the initial data set was found to affect the efficiency of the optimization process. Larger data sets result in faster optimization, requiring an average of 16 development cycles, while smaller data sets require 22 cycles. For practitioners this means, if only four data points are initially available, the additional acquisition of 16 data points to improve performance may not justify the savings of a mere six experiments. Overall, the number of initial samples does not seem to affect which model-pipeline combination produces the best results, i.e., there is no approach that is particularly well suited for small initial data sets but not for larger initial data sets. Performance appears to be invariant in this regard.

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Figure 11: Comparing the performance in terms of required development cycles for different initial training set sizes across 1350 experiments respectively.

Our third question (Q3) explored the impact of optimization strategies on SL performance, particularly the advantage of integrating external data, such as CO₂ footprints, into the model. Our findings, shown in Figure 12, indicate that using a-priori environmental information, often available at a lower cost than extensive laboratory data, not only aligns with ecological priorities but also significantly enhances the performance of SL. The integration of such external data into the design process, though seldom discussed in the literature, appears to have a profound effect on reducing the number of development cycles required. This approach not only leverages ecological data to inform better material design but also exemplifies how sustainability considerations can be seamlessly integrated into technological advancements in material science.

Figure 12: Comparing the performance in terms of required development cycles for different design targets with only compressive strength shown in yellow and compressive strength and CO₂ footprint shown in purple, each based on 1350 experiments respectively.

One of the most significant outcomes of our research is demonstrating the potential of SL to dramatically reduce the number of experimental iterations required in the development of new, environmentally friendly building materials. In optimal conditions, using SL allowed for sampling less than 5% of the potential formulations to identify suitable materials with high certainty. This represents a substantial improvement over traditional methods, which typically require sampling 100% of potential formulations.

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4.1.2. Conclusions

This case study confirms that the strategic configuration of SL-driven material design processes, including the choice of models and optimization strategies, plays a crucial role in enhancing the efficiency and effectiveness of discovering new building materials. By adopting approaches that intelligently integrate ecological considerations and leverage advanced machine learning techniques, we can foster the development of sustainable materials that meet the stringent demands of both industry standards and environmental conservation. Our research provides a scalable and adaptable framework that can be applied broadly across the construction industry, promoting faster adoption of sustainable material solutions, and contributing to global sustainability efforts, aligning with goals such as those outlined in the Paris Climate Agreement.

Overall, we assume that the real performance is significantly better than shown here. After all, the data on which these analyses are based comes from all over the world and is therefore inconsistent. The data quality from a laboratory, on the other hand, is likely to be significantly higher, so that these results can even be regarded as a reliable lower bound estimate.

Interestingly, the effectiveness of SL was not directly correlated with the conventional measure of model accuracy, such as RMSE. Instead, the ability of the models to expedite the discovery of optimal materials was better evaluated by their performance in simulated experiments, which directly measured the number of development cycles required to meet design targets. This approach challenges the traditional emphasis on model accuracy in materials development and underscores the value of a practical, results-oriented framework for SL in building materials design.

The study also highlighted that incorporating ecological considerations—specifically the CO₂ footprint—into the design process does not compromise the mechanical performance of the materials. This finding is crucial as it suggests that the dual goals of environmental sustainability and material performance can be simultaneously achieved, paving the way for more holistic approaches to sustainable building practices.

4.2. LLM based design – a systematic benchmark

Our second case study focuses on evaluating a novel design methodology, Context Driven Design (CDD), which leverages LLMs to enhance the development of eco-friendly building materials. This approach is based on our preliminary explorations [23], is detailed in a study currently under review in the Digital Discovery Journal and is available as a pre-print [31]. The research employs a subset of our comprehensive open-source dataset, which includes 240 formulations of AAC using FA and GGBFS as binders.

Each formulation in this dataset contains documented 28-day compressive strengths. Key formulation parameters include the amount of binder used, the water-to-cement (W/C) ratio, blending ratios of FA and GGBFS, and the curing methods applied. The primary goal of this study was to rapidly identify high-performance materials within this dataset over a fixed set of 10 development cycles. Essentially, this involved

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using an LLM for suggesting the most promising formulation and measuring the highest performing materials that could be identified within a fixed laboratory budgets of ten validations of the suggested recipes.

Our core hypothesis was that CDD, by effectively utilizing natural language to integrate and leverage fuzzy domain knowledge, could significantly streamline the material design process. The research aimed to answer several critical questions regarding the effectiveness and efficiency of CDD in comparison to traditional design methods:

The central question of our study was to determine whether the performance of current chat models, specifically GPT-3.5 and GPT-4, is sufficient to position them as viable alternatives to established tools like Bayesian optimization using Gaussian process regression in the domain of AAC formulation. This inquiry is crucial as it explores the potential for these advanced language models to disrupt traditional optimization methodologies in material science, particularly in the formulation of eco-friendly building materials.

Additionally, we sought to identify the key factors that drive the performance of these large language models, especially focusing on enhancements that can be applied post-training. Understanding these factors is vital for optimizing the models' application in real-world scenarios, where the ability to adapt and refine outputs based on iterative feedback can significantly enhance their utility and effectiveness.

Figure 13: Benchmarking the CDD approach in different configurations. Left: Variations of the system message including three different levels of design knowledge, each in three rephrased versions, respectively. Center: Model selection; Right: Implemented reasoning strategies ZSD and TVD.

The experimental program, illustrated in Figure 13 was designed to analyze the statistical performance across 30 design runs for each setup configuration. The chat models were configured with two variations of system messages as context (see Figure 13, left). The first variation included both instructions (such as ‘You are tasked to create a concrete mix design!’) and explicit design rules (such as ‘A higher W/C-ratio reduces strength’), while the second comprised only instructions without additional design rules.

The study employed two chat models: GPT-3.5-Turbo and GPT-4-Turbo (see Figure 13, center). For the GPT-3.5-Turbo, two reasoning strategies were tested (see Figure 13, right): simple ZSD and TVDL which extends

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the ZSD by a second verification Loop (compare section 3.2). Conversely, the GPT-4-Turbo was exclusively tested using the ZSD scheme, focusing on its ability to generate viable material formulations without prior specific training.

For a robust comparison, baseline models including Gaussian Process Regression (GPR) and Random Forest (RF) commenced with four random samples as initial training data. The Random Draw (RD) method randomly selected samples at each of the development stages. This extensive baseline data provides a critical framework for evaluating the effectiveness of the innovative CDD approach in the realm of sustainable material development.

4.2.1. Key Findings and Innovations

Our research confirmed that CDD, when compared directly with established DDD baselines, exhibits slightly superior performance in achieving higher lower-bound strength in material formulations (see Table 1). This outcome was particularly notable given the unstructured and fuzzy nature of natural language inputs used in CDD. The analysis suggests that these results are largely attributed to "eureka moments" evoked by the context of the prompts within the LLMs, where innovative solutions were spontaneously but consistently generated across various prompts. These finding challenges conventional approaches and demonstrates the unique value of natural language processing in materials design.

Table 1: Benchmarking results. Left: Comparison of the 10% lower limits of the cumulative 28-day compressive strength: Values recorded at the (final) 10th development cycle.

Context	Model	Reasoning Strategy	Compressive strength in 10 th dev. cycle (MPa)
No Design Context	GPT-3.5 Turbo	ZSD	60
		TVD	56
	GPT-4 Turbo	ZSD	55
Design Context	GPT-3.5 Turbo	ZSD	60
		TVD	62
	GPT-4 Turbo	ZSD	59
Gaussian Process Regression			60
Random Forrest			60
Random Draw			51

The

quality of contextual information provided to the LLMs significantly enhanced their performance. Integrating rich, contextual data into the CDD process led to substantial improvements, underscoring the importance of context in optimizing AI-driven methodologies. Much of this design knowledge, autonomously generated by GPT-4, showcases the potential for AI to not only participate in but actively enhance design software capabilities, creating adaptable and precise solutions for specific material challenges.

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The TVD reasoning strategies, using GPT-3.5-Turbo as the verifier model, showed systematic improvements in performance by allowing the model to consider and refine outcomes based on prior results, effectively using a feedback loop to optimize the design process. This approach was beneficial in addressing complex material design rules that require inference from multiple, sometimes conflicting, causal factors. The versatility of the TVD approach highlighted its potential to enhance the predictability and reliability of material formulation outcomes.

While GPT-4-Turbo generally exhibited higher mean design performance, indicating greater reliability, it was GPT-3.5-Turbo that achieved the best final performance in specific configurations at a significantly lower cost. This result indicates that newer versions of LLMs, while more advanced, do not necessarily guarantee superior outcomes in all scenarios and that cost-effectiveness remains a crucial factor in model selection.

4.2.2. Conclusions

In conclusion, the case study underscores the viability of LLMs as effective tools in the realm of sustainable building materials design. This approach, facilitated by the straightforward use of natural language, represents a significant shift from conventional data-driven design methods, offering a more accessible alternative that simplifies interactions with complex AI technologies. Such accessibility is likely to enhance the adoption and usability of digital tools in construction, broadening their appeal to a diverse range of practitioners. T

The systematic benchmarking of LLMs within this study demonstrates that their performance is comparable to traditional design methods. This finding is crucial as it positions LLMs not only as capable alternatives but also highlights their potential to harness collective knowledge and transform it into actionable designs for sustainable construction. This capability could significantly advance the dissemination of sustainable building practices, making high-quality, eco-friendly material design more feasible across the construction industry.

However, a notable aspect of our findings pertains to the spontaneous 'eureka moments' observed during the use of LLMs. While these moments did contribute to the high-performance solutions generated, their non-systematic and unpredictable nature raises concerns about the repeatability and reliability of such outcomes. This underscores the necessity for further research to understand the underlying mechanisms and conditions that favor such outcomes. Ensuring that these innovative solutions can be consistently replicated in future applications is essential for their practical deployment in material design.

Overall, this research not only demonstrates the capabilities of LLMs in advancing sustainable materials design but also lays the groundwork for future explorations that could refine these models for broader design applications. Moving forward, it will be crucial to develop methodologies that enhance the predictability and reliability of LLM outputs, ensuring that the AI-driven innovations in material design can effectively contribute to the goals of environmental sustainability and circularity in construction.

5. SLAMD – An AI Software for Sustainable Building Materials Lab

The results of our benchmarking studies vividly demonstrate that the application of machine learning significantly streamlines the complexity traditionally associated with formulation design in the laboratory. The integration of a-priori information such as carbon footprint estimations into the ID process facilitates a more targeted selection of materials that are not only structurally sound but also environmentally sustainable.

This methodological innovation led to the development of SLAMD (Sequential Learning App for Materials Discovery), a cornerstone digital innovation of the Reincarnate project. SLAMD is engineered to harness the principles of inverse design and integrate them seamlessly into laboratory workflows, providing material scientists and chemists with a novel tool for crafting sustainable materials. This software is not merely a technological leap forward; it represents a paradigm shift in how materials are conceived and optimized in research settings.

As the construction industry faces escalating pressure to mitigate environmental impacts and enhance sustainability, the demand for ground-breaking solutions becomes increasingly urgent. SLAMD is our strategic response to this challenge, blending advanced technology with user-centred design to expedite the development of sustainable materials. Such efficiency is essential, not only for accelerating research and development cycles but also for achieving the rapid progress required to meet global sustainability goals.

SLAMD features a sophisticated 'Digital Lab' and AI Optimization components, integrated within an intuitive user interface (see Figure 14). Each component is designed to function cohesively, augmenting both the tool's capabilities and the user experience. This synergy ensures that SLAMD is both a potent instrument for creating eco-friendly materials and a practical solution that aligns smoothly with the operations of modern laboratories.

The architecture of SLAMD bridges the gap between complex artificial intelligence models and their practical applications, ensuring that the advantages it offers are accessible to a diverse user base. From seasoned researchers to laboratory technicians with minimal programming skills, the tool's inclusivity is crucial for fostering broad adoption and maximizing its impact across various fields.

The source-code is freely available and has been published under an MIT license [32]. To enhance the utility and accessibility of SLAMD, we have developed a comprehensive suite of supporting resources. This package is detailed in our code repository and includes extensive documentation [33], a technical journal paper [34], that delves into the underlying methodologies, a video tutorial showcasing a demo design project, and an AI-powered chatbot [35]. designed to provide instant answers to user queries.

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SLAMD's deployment flexibility as both a local Python application and a web-based tool underscores its adaptability and broad applicability. This versatility ensures that SLAMD can be effectively implemented in diverse environments—from personal research laboratories to educational institutions and industrial settings—thereby amplifying its potential impact. This tool is poised to become an indispensable asset for anyone engaged in the development of sustainable building materials, driving innovation and sustainability in the construction industry forward. While our initial focus has been on waste-based concrete, the methodologies we've developed are versatile enough to be applied to other materials such as glass, steel, and ceramics.

Figure 14: SLAMD landing page with navigation bar (top) and overview over modules below.

5.1. Workflow

SLAMD combines a **Digital Lab** and **AI optimization**: The Digital Lab provides a framework for describing resources and processes and their ecological and-economic impacts and automates the creation of complex concrete recipes with detailed materials model. The AI optimization component integrates data from the Digital Lab and lets the user specify its exact requirements. The data dashboards assist the design of highly complex cementitious materials.

The design process in the Digital Lab begins with the creation of base materials and processes, which are the fundamental building blocks for more complex material formulations. Users can define various types of base

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materials such as powders, liquids, aggregates, and custom types, each tailored with specific properties relevant to their usage scenarios. These properties can include cost and environmental impact metrics, which are crucial for designing sustainable materials. Custom properties can also be added to adapt the base material to specific needs, providing flexibility in the design process.

Once base materials are defined, SLAMD allows users to create blended materials by combining two or more base materials. This blending process considers the properties of each base material and uses their respective proportions to calculate the properties of the blended material. This feature is particularly important to specify fine-tuned mixes of various resources (e.g. powder blends), which are common in sustainable materials.

With base and blended materials ready, users can proceed to formulate these materials into usable end products. This stage involves the selection and proportioning of various materials to create a concrete mix that meets predetermined criteria. While creating mixes manually can be very time consuming, the SLAMD material model allows users to set a whole range of ratios and weight proportions for components such as cement, aggregates, and water with just a few mouse clicks, creating thousands of feasible recipes.

5.2. AI Optimization for Materials Discovery

SLAMD's "Materials Discovery" module offers a streamlined approach to finding sustainable building materials by simplifying the management and visualization of complex data. This tool is designed to be accessible for users without in-depth programming knowledge, such as material scientists and chemists working towards environmentally friendly solutions.

At the core of the module is the ability to handle data effortlessly. Users can access design spaces from the Digital Lab or upload and modify material data through a straightforward interface. Data can be easily updated with new information directly from laboratory results.

The process of specifying material requirements is also made user-friendly within SLAMD. Users can define and adjust the requirements of the materials they need, such as mechanical and durability properties as well as sustainability and economic requirements. This precise tailoring ensures that the design process focuses on finding materials that meet specific criteria.

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Figure 15: Discovery modul with AI-optimization dashboard. Top: Design problem specification with input, target, and a-priori information. Bottom: Interactive scatterplot showing trade-off between predicted material strength and CO₂-footprint to enhance materials selection.

Moreover, SLAMD provides powerful data dashboards that help users navigate and understand the vast array of material options (see Figure 15). These dashboards display interactive plots and tables that sort materials based on their potential utility, helping users quickly identify and select the best candidates for further

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testing. Color-coded visualizations further aid in this selection process by highlighting materials that best meet the desired properties.

Overall, the Materials Discovery module in SLAMD simplifies the complex process of material design. By integrating easy data management, precise specification capabilities, and intuitive data dashboards, SLAMD enables users to make informed decisions quickly and efficiently. This tool not only accelerates the development of new, sustainable materials but also ensures that these innovations are accessible to a broad range of researchers and practitioners in the field of material science.

5.3. SLAMD Design Assistant

SLAMD's Design Assistant (see Figure 16) has been integrated to streamline user interaction and enhance the functionality of the SLAMD platform. This tool is particularly beneficial for new or less experienced users, as it simplifies the initial setup process through an interactive dialog that guides them through creating a new project. This process involves querying the users about the resources available, such as different types of powders and liquids that can be used as starting materials. These details are then systematically transferred to SLAMD's backend and stored in the digital laboratory, making the setup process as straightforward as possible.

In addition to facilitating project setup, the Design Assistant tackles another significant challenge: the lack of training data. It employs our innovative approach introduced in Chapter 3.2 and validated in Chapter 4.2, leveraging a LLM to generate zero-shot binder and concrete mix designs. During interactions, the Assistant gathers specific information about source materials, optimization targets, and boundary conditions directly from the user. This data forms a detailed design context, which is then processed by the GPT-3.5 Turbo model to suggest viable material formulations.

These features of the Design Assistant significantly lower the barriers to effective use of the SLAMD software, making advanced material design more accessible to a broader range of users. This integration not only simplifies the process of entering specifications and starting new projects but also creatively overcomes the obstacle of insufficient initial data, harnessing collective human knowledge encapsulated in an advanced AI model to propose suitable formulations.

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Figure 16: Chat based user interface of the Design Assistants to guide user through initial project setup or to leverage LLMs for zero-shot materials designs.

6. Adopting Innovations

This chapter delineates the essential steps undertaken to transition our innovations from conceptual frameworks into tangible, real-world applications, emphasizing the readiness and market integration of our software tool, SLAMD. The structure of this chapter is organized into two main sections:

First, we detail the achievement of Technology Readiness Level 6 (TRL-6) for SLAMD, demonstrated through a rigorous laboratory case study conducted at TU-Berlin. This section showcases how SLAMD has been effectively applied in a real lab environment to develop complex, waste-based materials, confirming its capability and readiness for broader industrial use. The case study not only tests the tool's functionality but also its adaptability and efficiency in producing high-performance, waste-based building materials with complex composition under realistic conditions.

Following the technical validation, the chapter transitions to exploring how these innovations are being integrated into the market. Through workshops and collaborative sessions, academic and industry partners within our consortium have engaged in an active dialogue to identify and discuss case studies pertinent to their business interests. This part of the chapter highlights preliminary findings from these discussions, offering insights into potential changes in business practices and exploring actionable pathways for market impact. These interactions are crucial for understanding the applicability of our research in current market scenarios and for driving the adoption of sustainable innovations in the construction industry.

Together, these sections provide a comprehensive overview of how our technological advancements are not only scientifically viable but also practically and commercially relevant, paving the way for substantial impacts on sustainable construction practices.

6.1. TRL-6 Lab Study

Our software tool SLAMD has been subjected to rigorous validation in a laboratory setting, focusing on the development of complex, waste-based materials. This case study aims to highlight how SLAMD meets the criteria for Technology Readiness Level 6 (TRL 6), which involves demonstrating a technology in an environment that closely replicates its intended operational setting. The details of our study have been submitted for publication and are available as a pre-print [36].

The specific aim was to develop high-performance alkali-activated materials (AAMs) that achieved a compressive strength of greater than 100 MPa within 7 days. This target was established to demonstrate the software's capability in formulating high-performance construction materials that not only meet but potentially exceed industry standards for mechanical performance.

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The study was carried out in a real lab environment, using industrial-grade waste-materials to create alkali-activated binders from waste glass precursors. This setting not only provided a testbed that mirrors typical industrial conditions but also allowed for the exploration of high-variability material complexity, thus underscoring the practical relevance of the software. The use of various sodium-based activators and the optimization of these complex formulations through SLAMD demonstrate the tool's capability to handle real-world complexities in sustainable material design, thus meeting the environmental criteria for TRL 6.

6.1.1. Results

Throughout the case study, SLAMD was instrumental in navigating and optimizing the design space. Unlike the traditional Design of Experiments (DOE), which relies on a pre-defined experimental setup, SLAMD applied AI-driven strategies to dynamically explore and refine material formulations. This is shown in Figure 17 where SLAMD on the left took a free pathway towards high performance materials, whereas DOE followed a rigid structure, basically sampling from the corners of the design space. SLAMD's approach resulted in a more efficient and effective development process, markedly reducing the time and resources needed to achieve optimal material properties.

Figure 17: Lower dimensional representation of design spaces that were explored by DDD with SLAMD (A) and traditional DOE (B). The size of the points reflects the compressive strength reached after 7 days. The highest strength is marked with a star. The optimized mixture from DOE is marked with an X. The variation of the W/S ratio and the sodium sulphate content are not shown.

The average performance of materials developed through SLAMD was notably higher than those developed through traditional DOE methods (see Figure 18 below). Specifically, while SLAMD materials consistently achieved and surpassed the target in the final design stage, the DOE approach yielded only one mixture that barely reached the target strength of 100.2 MPa.

The experimental results using SLAMD demonstrated a significant progression in material performance over the course of the study. The highest compressive strength recorded was 125.5 MPa, well above the target of 100 MPa.

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Figure 18: The 7-day compressive strength results from the data-driven design and the design of experiments approach with the goal of achieving 100 N/mm². The respective design phases are indicated by the arrows above.

The results clearly favored SLAMD over DOE, showcasing superior qualities in the AI-driven designs such as achieving higher compressive strengths and a more reliable prediction of material behavior under various conditions.

6.1.2. Impact and Relevance

Significantly, this case study was conducted independently by a bachelor's thesis candidate, demonstrating the software's ease of use and accessibility. The independence of the research adds substantial credibility to the maturity and readiness of SLAMD as a tool for industry application. It highlights that even users with limited exposure to both materials design and the software can effectively outperform an industry-scale research study. This substantially supports that SLAMD can broaden the potential user base of AI design methods within the materials science and engineering community.

The outcomes of this study are not merely academic; they have practical implications that enhance the feasibility of deploying SLAMD in the construction materials industry. By demonstrating that SLAMD can outperform traditional methods in a real lab setting, the study supports the tool's readiness for wider adoption and integration into the standard practices of material development. This transition from a developmental tool to an industry-ready solution is critical for meeting the demands of modern construction, especially in the context of sustainability and efficiency.

In conclusion, the application of SLAMD in this controlled yet complex laboratory environment effectively demonstrates its readiness at TRL 6. The tool has proven capable of operating under conditions that closely mimic real industrial scenarios, providing a reliable, efficient, and accessible solution for the design of sustainable construction materials. This case study not only validates the practicality of SLAMD but also highlights its potential to transform material development processes across the construction industry.

6.2. Waste Cases (Ragn Sells, Sweden)

According to the UN Global Outlook 2019, approximately 50 percent of the world's greenhouse gas emissions, 90 percent of biodiversity loss, and 90 percent of water access threats are attributed to the extraction and processing of natural resources. With the depletion of traditional raw material sources, the energy required for extraction is increasing. In light of this, the circular economy paradigm emphasizes the transformation of materials currently deemed as waste into new raw materials, highlighting the importance of minimizing the use of increasingly scarce virgin resources rather than merely reducing waste volumes.

In the field of waste management and recycling, most innovation pipelines are aimed at upgrading waste into more valuable products, with the initial focus on the waste itself. However, Ragn Sells' innovation strategy reverses this approach and prioritizes the substitution of high-impact inputs in manufacturing. This approach addresses the challenges posed by heterogeneous materials in a regulatory environment still dominated by linear economic models. By reversing the development of the value chain, starting from the raw material needs of manufacturers and tracing back to the built environment, Ragn Sells aims to minimize the conversion of materials into waste. This historically resource- and time-intensive process is now being enhanced by tools such as SLAMD and other AI-assisted inverse experimental design technologies, fostering the creation of new circular value chains.

Ragn Sells is also pioneering technologies to treat various waste streams to recover critical materials, for example through processes such as Ash2Salt, Ash2Phos, and the conversion of oil shale ash to precipitated calcium carbonate (PCC). These processes not only recover essential elements, but also produce by-products, such as silica sand from Ash2Phos, which is suitable for use as a supplementary cementitious material (SCM) in concrete, meeting existing fly ash standards. In contrast, residues from other processes, such as Ash2Salt, may require further treatment before they can be used in a similar way.

In the plastics sector, Ragn Sells is exploring the use of recycled PVC and fillers to reduce the carbon footprint of PVC products. This approach is in line with the potential uses of PCC produced from oil shale ash, as seen in Estonia. Despite the existing challenges in material experimentation and specification, especially in companies with long-standing supplier relationships, tools such as SLAMD could significantly accelerate the identification and validation of potential material recipes and formulations.

In addition, future circular economy activities at Ragn Sells will explore sustainable alternatives and innovations across a range of materials. This includes particleboard and MDF, where alternative binders and resins will be evaluated for their environmental impact and performance. The scope of innovation will also extend to the development of environmentally friendly formulations for paints and sealants, as well as improving the recyclability of various types of plastic flooring. In addition, research will focus on the creation of sustainable coatings and the use of environmentally friendly clays to maintain functionality while

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minimizing the environmental footprint of these products. These initiatives represent promising avenues for advancing material sustainability and reducing the environmental impact of production and use.

6.3. Designing Concrete with Recycled Aggregates (Cemex Poland)

Our partner Cemex Poland has proactively integrated the SLAMD tool into its research and development activities, focusing on optimizing laboratory tests and enhancing the production of concrete using recycled aggregates. This initiative aligns with the European Union's ambitious recycling targets, which include achieving a 55% recycling rate for municipal waste by 2025 and 65% by 2035. Meeting these targets is crucial not only for compliance but also for advancing sustainable industry practices within the construction sector.

The variability in recycled aggregates, such as differences in carbonization, moisture content, and impurities, presents unique challenges in concrete production. These factors significantly influence the final product's properties, including porosity and permeability, which are critical to the structural integrity and durability of concrete. SLAMD's implementation and its ID approach allow Cemex Poland to efficiently navigate these complexities. The tool enables targeted exploration of different types of recycled aggregates and facilitates the prediction of optimal concrete formulations that meet predefined requirements for compressive strength, production costs, CO₂ emissions, and recycling rates from limited initial laboratory data.

Figure 19 illustrates the design space of various concrete formulations in a two-dimensional representation, where a few initial data points collected in Cemex's labs (represented by black crosses) are augmented by SLAMD to project insights onto a broader range of untested formulations. The colour coding in the figure indicates the expected utility of the novel designs, simplifying the selection process for materials that meet specific design requirements.

Crucially, SLAMD's framework for rapid exploration and reliable exploitation of machine learning models provides a strategic advantage in managing the complexities associated with sustainable building materials. This capability is particularly relevant in a market increasingly demanding environmentally friendly construction solutions. Moreover, SLAMD's intuitive user interface and comprehensive documentation have helped overcome typical barriers associated with implementing AI technologies in the concrete and cement sector.

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Figure 19: 2D representation of the materials design-space containing small lab data set (black crosses) from recycled concretes and the augmentation of the results onto manifold untested formulations. The colour indicates the expected utility of the novel designs.

Cemex's commitment to innovation is evident in its strategic use of SLAMD not merely as a testing tool but as a transformative component of its material development strategy. This proactive approach ensures that the company not only complies with regulatory frameworks and sustainability targets but also leads in adopting advanced technologies that can redefine industry standards.

In conclusion, Cemex Poland's active utilization of SLAMD exemplifies how industry partners in the Reincarnate Project are effectively translating theoretical research into practical, market-ready solutions. By doing so, they are not only advancing their operational capabilities but also significantly contributing to the project's overarching goals of reducing waste and CO2 emissions in the construction industry. The feedback from hands-on case studies continues to refine the development of SLAMD, underscoring its high adaptability and transformative potential for fostering more sustainable and efficient construction practices.

6.4. Data-Driven Design in Sustainable Asphalt Pavement Formulation (Mostostal, Poland)

Our partner Mostostal Warszawa recognises the potential use cases of applying material Data-Driven Design approach to some of their business activities. Although material production is not the core of their business, for the needs of ongoing infrastructure projects, as well as for external customers, Mostostal produces bitumen compounds internally. Therefore, as a general contractor they see the potential in scaling SLAMD functions and the idea of the digital laboratory twin to improve our asphalt concrete

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mixture formulation. With the help of AI-driven design methodology, the change in approach towards reusing reclaimed asphalt, which in Poland was automatically considered waste until recently, could be accelerated. This would support the implementation of European Union recommendations related to carbon neutrality and circular economy – Green Deal 2050.

In case of road renovation and reconstruction projects, the rates in which reclaimed asphalt is being recycled or reused in the asphalt mixture production process plays a crucial role in the transition from linear to circular economy. Use of DDD tools such as SLAMD could allow easier implementation of reclaimed asphalt. As this framework has proved to significantly reduce development time and costs in the design of concrete mixes it has analogical potential to support design of concrete pavement formulas.

In Poland in order to make the use of reclaimed asphalt wide-spread in renovation and reconstruction projects, the legal requirements associated with the loss of waste-status of this material have been streamlined in recent years. This proves that the demand for the use of recycled materials in road construction is high. Providing AI-driven solutions that support the design process incorporating reclaimed asphalt could furtherly support this step towards circular economy. Considering the complexity and variability of secondary resources such as reclaimed asphalt it is necessary to have an automated, intelligent development process to ensure that more sustainable asphalt formulation is feasible.

In summary, application of SLAMD to development of asphalt pavement formulas has potential to be a catalyst for reusing old asphalt materials. Successively, it can be used to promote environmental protection by significantly reducing the exploitation of non-renewable natural sources of raw materials, such as aggregates. DDD could lead to financial saving on road investments through increased amount of asphalt pavement recycling and overall reduced time of the design of material formulas. Making the implementation of sustainable practices easier and more attractive to an investor.

6.5. Use of Data-Driven Design for middle-sized building sites (3L, Germany)

As an architectural office 3L is focused on designing small to mid-sized buildings can greatly benefit from utilizing a data-driven AI materials design application known as SLAMD. This tool specializes in optimizing and designing materials by leveraging secondary raw materials, waste, and recycled materials according to user-defined specifications for specific applications. In the field of building construction, SLAMD can optimize the mechanical properties of recycled concrete, such as compressive strength and durability, to assess its suitability for structural elements like foundations, beams, and columns. This allows for a better integration of recycled concrete into construction designs, reducing dependency on traditional materials and minimizing the environmental impact.

In road construction scenarios, SLAMD can also improve the properties of recycled concrete mixes for use in pavement layers, subbases, and base courses. The tool's ability to optimize material properties (e.g., particle

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size distribution and stiffness modulus) to meet specific performance requirements promotes the development of durable and sustainable road infrastructures while limiting the consumption of natural resources.

In landscaping projects, SLAMD could be used to improve the sustainability of components such as retaining walls, pavers and decorative elements by increasing the proportion of recycled or sustainably sourced components while optimizing material performance depending on the application. This integration not only improves the aesthetic and environmental aspects of outdoor facilities, but also aligns with circular economy principles and promotes material reuse.

Overall, by adopting SLAMD, architectural offices can take a holistic approach to sustainable construction. The application supports technical design and decision-making processes, merging environmental, economic, and material considerations to optimize outcomes and advance the construction of resource-efficient, resilient, and environmentally responsible buildings in Germany.

6.6. Use of Data-Driven Design for Re-Use of Urban Facilities (VIAS, Spain)

VIAS has more than 90 years of experience and is one of the leading construction companies in Spain in terms of turnover and profitability. As a generalist construction company, it stands out for the construction and maintenance of important railway projects, highways and roads, airports, hydraulic works, coasts and ports, industrial and urban developments, building (residential and non-residential), and environmental projects. To highlight the performance in the construction and conservation of hydraulic works. The company is currently executing the largest hydraulic work that is currently under construction in Spain. It also carries out maintenance and conservation works on hydraulic networks and also the construction of WWTPs throughout the national geography, both new plant construction and expansions of existing facilities in operation, such as the WWTP in Albacete that is one of the demonstrators of the REINCARNATE project.

Water treatment plants are complex urban facilities beyond the buildings that are part of them. A wide range of different materials (concrete, metals, ceramic, glass, ...) can be obtained during demolition works while the expansion works of existing facilities in operation take place (often with the presence of contaminated materials). They also include many valuable products (pumps, valves, etc.) that might lend themselves for reuse. The materials obtained from demolition can have different uses, always following the current regulatory framework. It is usually necessary to carry out a large amount of laboratory tests what means money and time. In the case of WWTPs we have the added problem that some of the materials that are part of the facilities often suffer severe damage due to the chemical attack of the aggressive agents of water and the acid gases produced by wastewater. In this environment, a shorter useful life is assumed for the element and some potential new uses might be avoided.

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The software tool SLAMD is very interesting to rule out options and shorten times. The use of SLAMD can help limit the multiple options for material obtained from demolitions, with the benefits that this entails, such as reducing laboratory research times, opting towards alternatives with increased durability which is an essential factor of the green circular economy and even know in advance the carbon footprint of possible alternatives.

7. Conclusions and Recommendations

In fulfilling Task T3.3 of the Reincarnate project, significant strides have been made toward advancing the circular economy practices within the European construction industry. This task focused on developing data-driven methods to evaluate the compressive strength, workability, and durability of recycled materials, particularly aiming to enhance the valuation of these materials through innovative technological integrations.

Throughout the project period, a comprehensive approach was taken to address the various components outlined in the task description. Key achievements include the development of an open science data set, which has been meticulously curated from over 30 years of digital materials testing data held by BAM. This dataset, now comprising 1,630 waste-based concrete mixes complete with detailed analytical and destructive test data, serves as a critical resource for researchers and industry professionals alike. It adheres to FAIR standards, ensuring accessibility and utility across the board, and has been further disseminated through a dedicated journal publication.

Moreover, novel machine learning methods have been developed and validated, significantly advancing the capability to assess recycled materials. These methods have been integrated with carbon estimation techniques developed in earlier tasks, allowing for a holistic approach to material evaluation that prioritizes sustainability. This integration is encapsulated in the CP-IM system, which facilitates the optimization of material properties while considering environmental impacts. The effectiveness and innovation of these methods have been recognized in journal publications [23, 28, 30, 34] and pre-prints [31, 36, 37], contributing substantially to the body of knowledge in sustainable material design.

The project also saw the successful development and deployment of the SLAMD software at TRL-6, marking a major milestone in achieving practical, real-world applications of our research. SLAMD has been made freely available under an MIT license, ensuring broad accessibility and encouraging widespread adoption. Its capabilities have been rigorously tested in a large-scale lab study, the results of which are available as a pre-print, further demonstrating the software's effectiveness in creating high-performance, waste-based materials.

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Efforts to generalize the developed approaches to other materials have also been fruitful, with multiple hands-on workshops and discussions leading to the initiation of several case studies set to continue in subsequent work packages. These activities have not only solidified the groundwork for future explorations but have also fostered strong partnerships with industry stakeholders such as Cemex, who has begun implementing SLAMD in their operations.

These achievements align closely with Reincarnate’s mission to reduce construction and demolition waste by 80%, increase the reusability of materials, and cut sector emissions by 70%. By leveraging advanced digital technologies and fostering collaboration across the construction industry, the project has positioned itself as a pivotal player in promoting circular economy principles. The outputs of this task and their integration into the broader objectives of the Reincarnate project underscore the potential of digital innovations to transform traditional practices, driving sustainability in the construction industry at scale.

In summary, the successful execution of Task T3.3 has not only met but exceeded its objectives, delivering robust tools and methods that empower stakeholders to make informed decisions toward sustainability. The implications of this work are far-reaching, offering scalable solutions that support the transition to a circular economy while providing a blueprint for similar initiatives globally.

7.1. Recommendations

Building upon the outcomes of our Reincarnate project, we strongly recommend the application of the ID approach facilitated by the SLAMD tool across contexts where complexity currently hinders progress. The uniform success of SLAMD in optimizing the use of recycled materials in concrete suggests a high potential for broader application. Standardization bodies and governmental agencies, in particular, should consider embracing this technology to enhance material reuse and recycling processes. The formation of a RILEM focus group by Reincarnate partners from BAM within the technical committee for Data-Driven Concrete Science aims to disseminate these innovations and encourage their widespread adoption.

Additionally, the exploration of LLMs within this project has shown promising results in creating tangible material formulations through natural language processing. This approach provides a more accessible interface compared to traditional data-heavy ID methods, potentially democratizing the use of sophisticated modeling techniques. While the performance of LLMs has shown some inconsistencies, our investigations have begun to uncover the mechanisms that influence their output, suggesting pathways for further enhancement.

Given these findings, we recommend continued research into LLMs, particularly to refine and understand their application in material science. The intuitive nature of LLMs could significantly expand access to cutting-edge material formulation techniques, especially in regions where technical expertise and resources are

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limited. This could lead to a broader dissemination of best practices and accelerate the adoption of sustainable materials across the global construction industry.

In conclusion, the integration of SLAMD and the exploration of LLMs within the Reincarnate project have not only advanced our understanding of material reuse and recycling but also set the stage for significant technological and methodological shifts in the construction industry. These advancements align closely with Reincarnate's mission to reduce waste, enhance material reuse, and decrease emissions, ultimately contributing to the sustainability goals of the European construction sector.

7.2. CP-IM Inclusion

Integrating our innovative SLAMD tool into the CP-IM can significantly enhance the functionality and scope of the platform. The CP-IM provides a robust foundation for integrating diverse data streams. The integration of SLAMD within the CP-IM could effectively leverage the IoT data collected from buildings about to be demolished. This data might include detailed materials information aggregated via IoT devices, offering a unique opportunity to optimize material reuse directly through the platform. Utilizing a semantic data pipeline based on ontologies currently being developed in Reincarnate work package 1, SLAMD could dynamically adjust and optimize formulations based on the specific characteristics and availability of recycled materials. This capability would allow for the real-time application of materials science to maximize resource efficiency and sustainability in construction projects.

Additionally, by incorporating data from other sources such as Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) systems, cost information data sources, BIM-servers, and Geographical Information Systems (GIS), SLAMD can enhance its predictions and recommendations, providing a comprehensive tool for decision-making in material reuse. This integration not only streamlines the process of materials optimization but also aligns with the broader goals of the Reincarnate project by facilitating the development of sustainable building practices and reducing waste.

Figure 20 Integration of SLAMD with CP-IM

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The diagram in Figure 20 illustrates the integration of the SLAMD tool with the CP-IM platform. It depicts the flow of waste material information, specifically focusing on waste material A, from its initial collection (demolition, refurbishment, etc.) to its incorporation into the SLAMD tool. This information is then processed within the SLAMD framework, where it is classified and added to the initial material data pool. The SLAMD tool utilizes this data to generate material optimizations, which can then be applied to new construction projects. This integration demonstrates how the SLAMD tool can enhance the CP-IM platform by dynamically adjusting and optimizing material formulations based on the availability and characteristics of recycled materials. The process not only facilitates efficient material reuse but also aligns with the sustainable goals of the Reincarnate project.

SLAMD's web-hosting capabilities and intuitive user interface make it an ideal candidate for seamless integration into the CP-IM's user interface with minimal effort. By simply embedding a link to the SLAMD tool within the CP-IM platform, users can access advanced material optimization functionalities directly within their existing workflow environments. This ease of integration ensures that SLAMD can be readily adopted by consortium partners and other stakeholders, fostering widespread use and facilitating the continuous improvement of the platform based on user feedback and evolving functional requirements.

In conclusion, the integration of SLAMD into the CP-IM represents a strategic enhancement that aligns with the objectives of the Reincarnate project. It not only leverages cutting-edge technology to promote the reuse of building materials but also enhances the platform's capacity to support sustainable and economically viable construction practices across Europe. This integration ensures that the CP-IM remains at the forefront of technological advancements in the construction industry, driving forward the principles of a circular economy.

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